

QDR Curation Handbook

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This document provides an overview of QDR's internal curation process. The process includes standardized steps from depositor contact, file processing procedures and Dataverse operations, to publication of the data project and thereafter.

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Introduction

QDR's core essence, its *raison d'être*, is the storing, preserving, and publishing of qualitative and multi-method research data -- that is, *data curation*: maintaining the value and usefulness of data over time, and ensuring their availability and findability for re-use, in principle, in perpetuity.

This handbook attempts to cover the entire data curation process, from initial contact with data depositors to post-publication. It should serve both as a way to familiarize oneself with QDR's curation process as well as as a tool to be referred back to continuously. It is designed in the hope that one could read fairly straight through the document, with more technical and problem-specific guidance in linked documents that branch out of the main body.

The intent behind this published version of the handbook is three-fold. First, it provides an additional layer of transparency to QDR's internal operations. Second, it might serve as a resource for qualitative researchers interested in what qualitative data sharing entails and what qualitative data curation "in practice" looks like. Finally, we hope that this handbook proves to be useful across the growing community of qualitative data curators, that they may learn from it as much as we hope to learn from them.

The internal version of this handbook is a live document. As we encounter new challenges and find appropriate solutions, find ways to improve processes, or adopt better standards, the document continuously evolves.

1. Contact with Depositor

Before the deposit and curation process can begin, several steps need to be taken to ensure both an adequate fit with QDR's policies as well as a smooth and timely curation workflow thereafter. This includes an initial assessment of the proposed project, procedures for handling deposit fees and waivers, and collecting answers to curation-related questions such as metadata and de-identification.

1.1. Initial assessment

The aim of the initial assessment is to determine whether the project is desirable and feasible as well as the conditions under which it would go forward.

We pose the following questions:

- Is it in scope given QDR's [collection policy](#)?
- If data involves human participants, what consent language was used?
- Are there any potential copyright restrictions?
- Are there permissions to be obtained from other archives?
- Is the data associated with a publication and is there a publication deadline?
- Are there reasons to expect high costs of curation? If so, is there a budget?

For situations in which the data deposited are out of scope (e.g., purely quantitative), inquire whether they plan on submitting additional data and, if not, identify a more appropriate repository and refer them accordingly.

1.2. Curation Questions

If the initial assessment shows that we are able to curate the data, we continue with a list of questions we want to be able to answer prior to starting the curation process. They center around metadata, data organization, documentation, and de-identification.

1.2.1. Metadata

1. What is your ORCID? We recommend for every depositor to create an ORCID (orcid.org), if you don't have one already, and include it in the metadata
2. Are there other contributors to the data project?
3. Is there an associated publication we can link to in the data?
4. Did the project receive any funding that we could list?
5. From when to when was the data collected?
6. What is the temporal coverage of the data?
7. What is the geographical coverage of the data?
8. Is there a data abstract? This is a general description/documentation of the data, which should answer questions one the following lines, non-exhaustively:
 - a. What are the data?
 - b. How were the data selected?
 - c. How were the data collected?
 - d. How are the data organized?

1.2.2. Project Organization

1. What is the approximate number & size of the files?
2. How are they organized?
3. What would a folder structure look like?
4. Are changes required (file names esp.)?
5. Which files are documentation, which are data?

1.2.3. Documentation

Ask about the following documentation files, if relevant:

1. Informed consent script
2. IRB approved application
3. Interview guides or similar
4. Data list / archive log
5. Data Management Plan if one was formally created
6. Data Narrative
7. Existing qualitative data? → Encourage QDR link

1.2.4. De-Identification

In some cases, i.e. interview data, de-identification might be needed. In these cases, ask how the data were de-identified and what the risk for participants would be if their PII were revealed nonetheless.

Be clear that it is their responsibility; we can help, but they need to make the calls. See file processing procedures below for curation-related de-identification tasks, such as data sensitivity assessment, de-identification verification, and redactions.

2. File Processing Procedures

This section addresses all data processing procedures that occur *outside* of the Dataverse infrastructure, the data's final resting place. It includes a guide to useful software and scripts as well as the standardized process and step-by-step guide on how to get the data ready to upload onto the Dataverse.

2.1. Useful Software and Scripts

Below is a list with short descriptions of software and scripts referred to hereafter. More details are available under the respective links provided.

2.1.1. Software

R and RStudio

R is a programming language for statistical computing. Most of the customized programming for QDR, from web-scraping to curation assistance, is developed in R.

[Click on this link for download instructions](#)

RenameMaster

RenameMaster is a software that allows you to batch rename multiple files at once, very useful.

[Click on this link to download](#)

Note: Unfortunately RenameMaster does not work on MacOS. Instead, open the files in Finder. Select all files, right click and select "Rename Items". A box will appear at the top of the finder window called "Rename Finder Items". There you can, for example, select "Add text" "Before Name" and add the depositor name prefix to the filenames.

AutoMetadata

AutoMetadata is a software that allows us to bulk edit XMP tags, metadata, for PDF files. It allows simple editing of individual files as well as bulk operations. See instructions for very large applications.

[Click on this link for download and instructions for large applications.](#)

2.1.2. Scripts and Applications

VBA Scripts

Macro scripts are a programming code written in VBA language used in order to automate actions in MS Office. Below is a list of linked scripts that have been found useful for various curation tasks. Scripts are entered by holding Alt+F11 (opening VBA window) and clicking Insert>Module. F5 runs the script.

Separating worksheets into different workbooks:

Separating Excel worksheets is necessary because Dataverse only converts the first sheet into the .tab archival format. This can be easily done individually, but this script is helpful when dealing with a large amount of worksheets.

[Link to script on GitHub](#)

Password-protected Excel files:

It may be necessary to use a password-breaking VBA script if an Excel file is password-protected and needs to be edited (e.g., to allow for ingesting on Dataverse). This will work for passwords created in older Excel applications, but not in more recent versions.

[Link to script on GitHub](#)

Batch-converting .xls to .xlsx

Unfortunately .xls files will not ingest in Dataverse and are also a poor choice for preservation. This script automates the conversion process from .xls to .xlsx.

[Link to script on GitHub](#)

Batch-converting .txt to .doc

We typically don't convert .txt files to PDF. Where there are reasons to do so, converting .txt files directly to .pdf will leave a file path mark at the bottom of the pages, that is not desirable.

Converting it to a Word document first solves the issue. The following script automates the conversion process from .txt to .doc (files can then be converted to .pdf as normal).

[Link to script on GitHub](#)

R

Below is a list of helpful curation-related tools written in R by Sebastian Karcher. Click on the links for further instructions on GitHub.

Web Archiving Tool

Archivr automates preservation of URLs in Web Archives. The script can extract and archive all URLs on a webpage, Word document, or PDF file, and store them in the Way Back Machine (the Internet Archive) or via Perma.cc. Archiving URLs helps prevent link rot (when links cease to point to their originally targeted destination) by storing a preserved copy that will, presumably, always be accessible. It is also useful when content cannot be stored on QDR for copyright reasons.

[Link to the Web Archiving Tool and instructions on GitHub](#)

DVCurator

This is a very helpful R-package to assist in common curation processes. It creates and pre-fills GitHub projects and issues (where we track the curation workflow, see [section 2.2.](#)) and creates a data project work folder in dropbox. It can also download a list of files from Dataverse with associated metadata (important for file descriptions) as a .csv file.

[Link to dvcurator package and instructions on GitHub](#)

Other

DVUploader

Jim Myers developed DVUploader, a command line uploader for Dataverse. It's helpful for cases in which the amount of data is so large that the Dataverse interface has problems handling it (or if you keep running into 500 errors), bypassing it entirely. Make sure you have a current version of Java, download the DVUploader .jar file, store it in the file location of the files, access the command line interface by entering "cmd" in the file path line and run the following command line: `java -jar DVUploader-v1.0.7.jar -key=<api key> -did=<dataset doi> -server=<server URL> <dir or file names>`

[Link to DVUploader and instructions on GitHub](#)

2.2. Getting Organized

Using DVCurator in R (see [section 2.1.2](#)), create a new project in GitHub and a dedicated folder in Dropbox.

We use GitHub as a platform to manage projects. It is quite useful to that end and allows us to quickly see at which stage a particular project is currently at. DVCurator will automatically generate the GitHub project for you and you will find it [here](#).

- Projects are entitled: “<authorname> - <project title>” and use the “Automated kanban” template.
- We employ four “issues” tied to the project (the list of issue templates is available [here](#)). Assign at least yourself to all issues:
 - “<authorname> - Initial Deposit & Checks”
 - “<authorname> - Metadata”
 - “<authorname> - File Processing”
 - “<authorname> - Publication

DVCurator will also create a new dropbox folder named “QDR Project - <authorname>” including a file list and two subfolders. The first subfolder is entitled “Original Deposit”, and includes all the data from the data project on Dataverse. That data is never to be touched again, it will eventually be the only copy of the original data left as provided by the depositor. The second subfolder is entitled “QDR Prepared”. This is the folder in which we process the files, curate them, and prepare them for publication on QDR.

The folder structure within “QDR Prepared” can take different forms depending on the data project, but it is helpful to organize them in line with ordered processing steps. This way one does not inadvertently omit a step and has available back-ups if necessary (e.g., if file distortion occurs during optical character recognition - OCR). This can, but does not need to, look like this:

- 1_De-identification
- 2_PDF conversion
- 3_Renaming
- 4_OCR
- 5_Metadata
- 6_Archiving
- 7_Folder structure
- 8_Upload

As you work through the project, you can make notes in GitHub and check the issue boxes as each step gets completed. Move issues into “In progress” once you start working on them, and to “Done” once completed.

2.3. Making Data Ethically and Legally Sharable

Before sharing data, QDR ensures it can ethically and legally do so. Depending on the data project, this might involve data de-identification and evaluating possible copyright restrictions. Both tasks are discussed below.

2.3.1. De-Identification

When sharing human subjects data, interview transcripts for example, we are concerned about the risk that people could be identified when their consent agreement stipulated that their anonymity would be guaranteed. Therefore, we want to make sure that the data is sufficiently de-identified, in proportion to the [sensitivity of the data](#), the potential risk to participants, and (as much as possible) without compromising the data's integrity and future research value. This is usually done by the depositor, who is most familiar with the data and the human subjects.

In these cases, QDR verifies that the data is adequately de-identified, and may recommend further de-identification to the depositor. This of course includes PII (personally identifiable information, such as full names, phone numbers and addresses), but also contextual information, indirect identifiers, that could be sufficient for someone in the person's community, or even outsiders like us, to identify the person. This can include a combination of information such as age, number of kids, place of work, profession, location, etc. For small projects, we read through all files. For larger projects, we read through a wide sample and make a judgement call based on it.

In some cases, however, QDR will conduct further de-identification itself (e.g., [Boivin](#)) or even handle the entire de-identification process (e.g., [NIRI](#)). We prefer to redact and replace in Word by coding names and/or generalizing the data (e.g., a 72 year old becomes a [senior citizen]), but sometimes redacting PDFs in Adobe is necessary (e.g., scanned documents). In these cases, follow the redaction steps below:

- Do not highlight the passages in black
- In Acrobat, go to "Tools", select "Redact"
- Then select "Mark for Redaction" → "Text & Images"
- Mark all text/images to be redacted (they will have a red frame around them)
- Then click on "Apply"
- Do not remove identifying information from the document. We handle that through XMP metadata changes

When we do not have in-house language proficiency, consider using an automated translator -- but highlight the insufficiency of this to the depositor. In all cases, create a de-identification log

and make note of any involvement by QDR in the data processing note within the README file (cf. [section 2.12.1](#)).

[For further information, review QDR's de-identification guidelines here.](#)

2.3.2. Copyright

Another consideration is whether there are copyright restrictions in place that would prohibit QDR from publishing the data. This as well should be done by the depositor, but in some cases we need to advise the depositor or even review the data for copyright in full. A good example of this is the [Hispaniola data](#) deposited by Don Leonard. We investigate applicable copyright laws in the United States as well as any foreign jurisdictions from which the data originated if applicable (the latter mainly relates to government or other official publications; since QDR is in the US, US copyright rules apply to all documents). Each document is then reviewed and assessed on whether we can share the data. Data that cannot be shared can still be posted on QDR but needs to be restricted for all users until it enters the public domain.

Follow these general steps:

- (1) Investigate applicable copyright laws
- (2) Create a log file in Excel
- (3) Investigate and record who holds the copyright, restrictions, when it expired or is going to expire
- (4) If copyright licenses allow for sharing with attribution, edit files accordingly
- (5) Restrict files under copyright for all users on Dataverse: for normal files, access is usually granted to “:authenticated-users” (cf. [section 3.5](#)), for copyrighted files, simply omit the access grant
- (6) When copyright expiration date is known, add to the file description (cf. [section 3.3.2](#)) language akin to:
This file is currently under copyright and not accessible on QDR. The copyright expires in <YEAR>. The file will become available as it enters the public domain.
- (7) Add to the terms of access and use (cf. [section 3.5](#)) language akin to:
Files currently under copyright are restricted and not accessible to users. Where available, the year they enter the public domain (and will be available through QDR) is indicated in the file description.
- (8) Make note of it in the README file (cf. [section 2.12](#))
 - (a) under *****File Access*****, language akin to:
Files currently under copyright are marked with an asterisk. Where available, the year they enter the public domain (and will be available through QDR) is marked in square brackets.

(b) under *****Data Processing Note*****, language akin to:

Copyright status of the files was investigated and appropriate restrictions put into effect.

These steps are not necessarily taken consecutively in isolation of the curation process, i.e. a copyright review may be amongst the first things you do before processing the files and editing file restrictions in Dataverse amongst the last before publication.

2.4. File Conversions

After editing the files as necessary in their original format for de-identification and copyright, all files need to be converted to an archival format as follows:

- Formatted text files are converted to Adobe PDF - they will eventually be converted to PDF/A (cf. [section 2.9.](#))
Batch conversions can be done in either the file explorer (right click on selected files) or from within Adobe itself (create multiple PDFs)
- Image files are converted to JPEG Image .jpg
- Tabular files are converted to MS Excel .xlsx or .csv, which will ingest into .tab on Dataverse
For batch conversions, see applicable VBA scripts in [section 2.1.2.](#)
- Audio files are converted to MP3 Audio .mp3
- Video files are converted to MPEG-4 Video .mp4
- Qualitative Data Analysis Files (QDAS) (NVivo, ATLAS.ti, etc.) should be requested as REFI-QDA from the depositor if possible.

[Click here for more information on archival file formats \(and alternatives to the above\).](#)

Make note of any conversions and include them in the *****Data Processing Note***** of the README file, e.g. *.RM files converted to .MP4 using VLC media player version 3.0.8.0.* (cf. [section 2.12.1.](#))

2.5. File Editing

At this stage, the curator goes through each file individually. Files may need to be edited in order to improve secondary use or allow for ingesting on Dataverse (i.e., .tab format). Broken, duplicate, and unrelated files may need to be removed.¹

¹ In cases of broken or otherwise unusable files, you may be able to find a suitable copy online. If such a copy is not readily available, contact the depositor and request a workable version of the file.

Documents

Common editing needs in PDF formats include:

- Rotating pages - this is especially the case for scanned documents, where one regularly finds pages at 90 or 180 degrees (Ctrl+Shift+R)
- Separating PDF files - several documents are sometimes contained in one single PDF and need to be extracted
- Organizing pages - in case pages are out of order, not uncommon in scanned documents
- Deleting pages - in case of duplicates (Ctrl+Shift+D)

All this can be done in Adobe under the “Manipulate Pages” tab or with keyboard shortcuts.

A rare occurrence is the need to remove signed certificates that prevent changes to the pdf documents. This can happen even with public domain documents when officials lock them for editing. We do not, as of now, have a great solution for this. Printing to PDF does remove the certificates, but that creates unacceptably large file sizes upon PDF/A conversion. Current working protocol is to unlock the file(s) through an online converter.

Tabular Files

Editing of tabular files is mainly done in order to allow for ingestion to the .tab archival format on Dataverse. This includes:

- Separating worksheets into separate files - since upon conversion to .tab, only the first worksheet would be included. *This can be bulk automated for workbooks with many worksheets by using the applicable VBA script, see [section 2.1.2](#).*
- Editing cells so that each value has a row and column header (i.e. variables) - e.g. if a single cell spans multiple rows or columns, the ingest breaks. Consolidating the values in a single row/column fixes the issue (see [gh issue](#))
- Removing stray columns/rows to exclude variables with all missing values
- Removing line breaks, as of writing, this still prevents successful ingest (see [gh issue](#))

In some cases, an Excel file will contain textual data not in a tabular format and it cannot be manipulated to ingest. If that is the case, consider another preservation-friendly format like .tsv.

2.6. File Renaming

While the specific file-naming convention is determined for each data project individually, we rename files according to the following guidelines:

- At a minimum add a prefix of the depositor's last name to all files (“<authorname>_” - e.g., “Trachtenberg_”)
- Try to include the date on which the file was created in ISO format (YYYYMMDD)
- No spaces in filenames, use underscores (section spacing) and dashes or CamelCase (regular spaces)
- No non-ascii (e.g. accented) or special characters in filenames
- No more than 60 characters in filenames (creates problems in Windows and DB) and generally favor shorter filenames
- We might reflect the file type in the filename, e.g. _interview_
- We might reflect an organizational schema with folders/subfolders (e.g., book chapters)
- Identical filenames for different files are distinguished by a numbered suffix preceded by an underscore, e.g.: _1, _2, _3, ...
- For numbered lists exceeding one digit, we add zero(s) preceding the number in order to retain alphabetic order in other programs (e.g. _1 becomes _01 or _001 respectively)

You can edit filenames in the file explorer (use F2 and TAB for faster edits), but for other than small projects it quickly gets cumbersome. RenameMaster (cf. [section 2.1.1](#)) is a powerful tool for medium and large applications, allowing you to edit all files simultaneously (e.g. add “<authorname>_” to all files, find+replace in all). Simply copy the file path from file explorer and paste it into RenameMaster, all files in that folder will then show up and become editable.

2.7. File Metadata

QDR attaches metadata to all individual files in the data project, which improves file searches and provides file provenance information. Most commonly, this is done by editing XMP tags in PDF files, but it is also possible with a few other file formats.

2.7.1. PDF Documents

We edit XMP (Extensible Metadata Platform) tags in Autometadata (see [section 2.1.1](#)). You can edit them individually by opening the PDF in Acrobat under File>Properties>Additional Metadata... but that is rarely useful. When editing metadata for two or more files, using Autometadata is faster and more convenient.

Create a dedicated metadata folder (see [section 2.2.](#)) with all the PDF files, open Autometadadata and load the folder. We edit the XMP tags in the following manner:

Title: <Filename of the individual file>.pdf

Author: <last name>, <first name> (of the depositor)

Subject: QDR Data Project

Keywords: -

The keywords field is filled with a dash as a placeholder, which becomes necessary for technical reasons when processing large amounts of files.

You can edit the title field by copying the filename in the first column to the second column.* Best way to avoid the mouse and do several files consecutively, starting on the filename:

1. Ctrl+C
2. Right arrow
3. F2
4. Ctrl+V
5. Repeat for row below

All other fields (Author, Subject, and Keywords) can be edited all at once by selecting all files (Ctrl+A) and clicking Edit>Set Properties for Selected Records. Ignore the “Producer” field.

Make sure to click “Save Changes” at the end, and double check a sample PDF (in properties).

**When processing large amounts of files it quickly becomes tedious to copy/paste individually the filenames for the title field. [Click here for instructions on how to circumvent this for large operations.](#)*

2.7.2. Other formats

We generally only edit metadata in .pdf, .mp3 and .mp4 files, but have edited metadata for other file formats ad hoc previously and may standardize those procedures in the future.

For mp3 and mp4 files, metadata can be edited in VLC or Windows Media Player. In the past, we have only edited the “Artist” field to include the name of the depositor and QDR. For instance, in the [Trachtenberg Pedagogical Materials](#) project, we edited the “Album Artist” field for the mp3 course recordings to read: “Marc Trachtenberg; Qualitative Data Repository (QDR)”.

We have edited metadata in Excel files, but those were cases in which we had to *remove* identifying metadata fields (e.g., “Manager”, “Author”, “Last Modified By”) for blind peer review. In principle, Excel metadata could be edited to reflect provenance as well.

2.8. Optical Character Recognition & Optimization

Next, and this mainly applies to PDF documents that were generated through scanning and/or conversion from image file formats, we run optical character recognition (OCR) to enable full-text search of the document. We also “optimize” the PDF, which reduces its file size by removing embedded fonts, compressing images and removing items from the file that are no longer needed.

This can all be done in Acrobat. Follow the steps below:

1. Create an empty destination folder for the OCR'd/Optimized files
2. Go to Tools>Action Wizard
3. Select “Optimize Scanned Document”, this will run both OCR and Optimization
4. Select “Add Files...” and select all files in the metadata folder
5. Right click on “Add Document Description” and click “Skip this Step” (if you don’t, this will delete all your metadata edits)
6. Click “Save As” and select “Save to Local Folder”, select the folder you created in step 1.
7. Click “Start” and let the process run, double-check that all files were processed by making sure that the total number of files in the metadata folder matches the number of files in the destination folder.
8. Review files for any potential problems (e.g., distortion) and OCR accuracy (if OCR completely fails or is unusable, revert to original).

2.9. File Archiving

After all editing is completed, files need to be converted to their final archival format. For most file formats that will already have been done beforehand (see [section 2.4.](#)), but PDF documents need to be converted to PDF/A -- an ISO standard for archiving and long-term preservation --, after which they can no longer be edited.

Similar to above, this is done in Acrobat’s Action Wizard. Follow the steps below:

1. Create an empty destination folder for the archived files
2. Go to Tools>Action Wizard>Archive Documents
3. Select “Add Files...” and select all files in the OCR folder or the metadata folder (if you did not run 2.8.)
4. Right click on “Add Document Description” and click “Skip this Step” (if you don’t, this will delete all your metadata edits)
5. Leave Preflight as it is

6. Click “Save As” and select “Save to Local Folder”, select the folder you created in step 1.
7. Click “Start” and let the process run, double-check that all files were processed by making sure that the total number of files in the original folder matches the number of files in the destination folder.
8. If the numbers match, also check the report and look for any possible errors (you can access it by clicking on “Full Report” below the “Save to Local Folder” field after the action is completed)

Note that Acrobat converts standard to PDF/A-1b. If you notice errors and the conversion fails, the PDF has remaining features that are incompatible with that archiving format. In that case, remove “Hidden Information” (under “Protection”) such as file attachments - but be careful not to remove the metadata. Otherwise, try conversion to PDF/A-2 (allows some embedded files) or PDF/A-3 (no limitation) as last resort.

Large operations: the tool seems to only support batch conversions of up to 420 files at a time. Each file takes ca. 8 seconds depending on file size (i.e. 450 files per hour once running properly). You will be periodically prompted to OK a particular PDF with out-of-range dimensions or other issue, after which you have to click “Start” again (so you can’t really leave it alone). It may crash at some point - but since you saved the archived files in a clean destination folder, you will know exactly where to pick up again.

File check: as you see the files appear one after the other on your screen, take this final opportunity to look out for any distorted or abnormal files if you have not already done so. In rare cases, especially if dealing with large amounts of files, files can become visually distorted somewhere along the file processing procedure. If such a case is identified, try to run the process individually and manually based on an original copy of the file. So far, this has always solved the problem (as long as the original file itself is not corrupt).

2.10. Archiving Webpages and Videos on the Web

In some cases, because of copyright reasons or because the aim is to prevent link rot (the occurrence of broken or dead links), we do not store data files on QDR itself but provide a URL to an archived copy of the content on the web. We use Perma.cc (similar to the Wayback Machine, though it functions only through user request) for static webpages and Webrecorder.io for streaming media (e.g., YouTube videos).

After generating the archived URLs, we provide both the original and archived links in a separate tabular file uploaded onto the data project. For an example using Perma.cc, see the [News Archive in the Gonzales-Ocantos data project](#). For an example using Webrecorder.io, see the [archived videos in the Wedeen data project](#). Both have been used for archiving external links in ATI annotations as well.

2.10.1. Static Webpages - Perma.cc

To create permanent records of web sources with Perma.cc, follow the instructions below:

1. Log in to and access the [Qualitative Data Repository page on Perma.cc](#)
2. Create a new subfolder under QDR titled with the last name of the depositor
3. Copy-paste a URL and click on “Create Perma Link”
4. You can bulk archive a list of URLs at once by clicking “create multiple links”, and copy/pasting a list from an excel file for example.
5. Download all URLs for the data project by clicking on the icon below. That will provide a csv file with the original URL, the title of the webpage, and the archived URL.

If the URLs are embedded in a text document or webpage (e.g., footnotes), instead of extracting them manually use the Web Archiving Tool (see [section 2.1.2](#)). The tool will automatically extract all urls out of the document, archive them via Perma.cc, and provide you with a list of original and archived URLs in a csv file.

2.10.2. Streaming Media - Webrecorder.io

To create permanent records of streaming media with Webrecorder.io, follow the instructions below:

1. Log in to and access the [Qualitative Data Repository page on Webrecorder.io](#)
2. Create a new collection under QDR titled with the last name of the depositor
3. Create a list under the collection, e.g. “<ProjectName> Archived Videos” and list it as private until ready to publish
4. Click on “New Session”, paste the URL and start recording
5. If satisfied, access the record under “Pages” (which should always remain private) and move it to the list you created in step 3
6. Make sure to create a separate record listing at least the original and corresponding archived URLs -- as of writing, you cannot yet download a tabular file listing all URLs.

For an example, look at the [Wedeen Project](#).

2.11. Folder Structure

Now that all files have been created and processed, we can organize them in a folder structure if warranted. Smaller projects may not have a folder structure, but larger ones will typically be organized by substantive categories or will reflect the organizational schema of the associated publication (by book chapters, for example).

Creating the folder structure now is necessary to build the organized file list for the Readme file and will eventually be reflected in the data project on the Dataverse.

2.12. Readme File

A Readme file is a form of documentation that contains information about other files in an archive. We always create a Readme file (either in Notepad or Notepad++) and name it README_<AuthorName>.txt

2.12.1. Readme Template

The Readme follows the following structure, sections in **bold** are almost always included (you can copy paste this template into notepad and edit it there):

****Title****

<project title>

****Suggested Citation****

Please cite any data used from this data project as follows:

<copy-paste Dataverse-generated citation>

****Description****

<copy-paste text from 'description' field> [see [section 3.4.\(6\)](#)]

****File Access****

Documentation freely accessible under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 license.

Data files accessible without restrictions for all registered QDR users under our Standard Download Agreement.

[edit file access if additional restrictions are put in place - e.g., see templates for copyright restrictions in [section 2.3.2.\(8\)\(a\)](#)]

****Included Files****

This collection contains the following files: [or files and folders, if applicable]

<insert file list, see below ([2.12.2.](#)) for instructions>

****Data Processing Note****

The data were processed according to the Qualitative Data Repository's curation policy. All files were checked for integrity. Files were checked to make sure they match documentation and consistent file names were applied. PDF files were converted to PDF/A using Adobe Acrobat Pro DC Version 2020.006.20034, XMP tags edited using AutoMetadata Version 1.0.0.20.

[edit data processing note according to processing steps, note everything we did with the data -- e.g., add notes on de-identification (2.3.1.), copyright (2.3.2.), and other file conversions (2.4.) -- and update software versions as necessary]

These data were obtained from the Qualitative Data Repository (QDR - <http://qdr.syr.edu>), a dedicated archive for storing and sharing digital data (and accompanying documentation) generated or collected through qualitative and multi-method research in the social sciences. QDR is supported by the National Science Foundation. Please consult QDR's General Terms and Conditions of Use (<https://qdr.syr.edu/termsandconditions>).

2.12.2. Obtaining the File List

The file list can take two forms, depending on whether they are organized in a folder structure or not. In either case, first create the draft Readme and place it with the other files (outside of the folder structure, if applicable), this way the Readme is included in the filelist.

File List Without Folders

1. Go to the folder with all the files, hold the mouse **over the white area to the right of the file list**, hold Shift and Right Click, and select “Open PowerShell window here”
2. Type: “Get-ChildItem -Name” and press Enter
3. Copy the file list and paste it into an MS Word file
4. Select all (Ctrl+A) and reformat into a numbered list (i.e., 1. 2. 3. 4.)
5. Copy-paste the numbered list under ****Included Files**** in the Readme
6. Move the Readme on top of the filelist, if not already there

File List With Folders

1. Go to the folder with all folders of the project (created in [section 2.11](#)), highlight the address bar (filepath), type “cmd” or “cmd.exe”, and press enter:

2. In the command-line interface that opens, edit and paste:

```
tree /a /f > FolderStructure_<ProjectName>.txt
```

and press enter.
3. This will create a text file in the same folder as the listed files and folder structure. Open the newly created .txt file and copy its content under ****Included Files**** in the Readme.
4. Move the Readme on top of the filelist, if not already there.

3. Dataverse Operations

This section addresses all procedures *inside* the Dataverse infrastructure. This includes instructions on how to upload the data, editing data-level metadata, editing project-level metadata, and final preparation steps for publication.

3.1. Data Collections

Data projects may be linked together in groups that we call data collections. These data collections could represent groups of projects by the same author (e.g., [The Trachtenberg Papers](#)), projects affiliated with a particular journal (e.g., [Security Studies](#)), or with a particular research group (e.g., the [Palliative Care Research Cooperative](#)).

Data collections should ideally be created *before* the data projects in them (transferring a project to a collection after the fact can only be done by a Super Admin). If applicable, follow the procedure below:

1. On the Dataverse main page, click on New Project > New Collection
2. Fill out the metadata fields and write a description for the data collection
 - a. The “Identifier” will be the collection’s URL, keep it short and do not use spaces
 - b. In general, leave the box for “use metadata fields from QDR Main Collection” in “Metadata Fields” and the box for “use browse/search facets from QDR Main Collection” checked
3. Click Save Changes
4. Go to Edit > Theme + Widgets > Theme
 - a. Upload a suitable image (usually from one of the data projects) to serve as a banner for the data collection
 - b. Add a website URL if applicable
5. Within the data collection, click on New Project > New Data Project
6. Copy the metadata from the previous draft project (in QDR Main Collection) to the new data project in the data collection
7. Continue by uploading the files as outlined below ([section 3.2.](#))

Note that for nested collections (e.g., ETS > Go Discuss), roles need to be assigned at each level separately. Depositors need to be given both a Dataset creator and a Member role.

3.2. Uploading the Files

In almost all cases, we upload the data using the Dataverse interface. Follow the steps below:

1. If the data is organized in folders, but it all in a zip file (this will carry the folder structure over):
Ctrl+A > RightClick > Send to > Compressed (zipped) folder
2. In the data project on Dataverse, click on “Upload Files” and drag+drop all files (or the zip file) there
3. Select all *data* files (i.e. unselect all documentation files like the Readme)
4. Click Edit > Restrict
5. Unless you wish to edit file descriptions now, click “Save Changes”
6. A window prompt will come up asking for the Terms of Access

a. For standard access, copy-paste the following:

```
<p>Documentation freely accessible under the <a  
href="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/">Creative  
Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 license</a>.</p>  
<p>Data files accessible without restrictions for all registered QDR  
users under our <a  
href="https://qdr.syr.edu/discover/standarddownload">Standard  
Download Agreement</a>.</p>
```

b. For special access conditions: edit as necessary (see templates in [section 3.5](#)).

The license for documentation files is always the same.

7. In most cases, select “Enable Access Request” (see [section 3.5](#) for cases in which access request should be disabled)
8. Select “Continue” - all files are now uploading onto the data project

Note:

1. The default upload limit is 1000 files and 18.6GB per file. If you reach beyond this limit, coordinate with Super Admin to lift the default restrictions. You may also divide data into upload-friendly portions or, in extreme cases, bypass the Dataverse interface completely by using DVUploader (see [section 2.1.2](#)).
2. Sometimes changes to the terms of access language are warranted, cf. [section 3.5](#). The same language is also used for the Terms of Use

3.3. Data-Level Metadata

Now that the data is uploaded, we allocate tags to the data and, in some cases, individual descriptions.

3.3.1. Allocating File Tags

Although custom tags are possible and some depositors choose to employ them, we allocate only four types of tags: ATI Annotations; Documentation; Code; and Data. Dataverse will sort the files in that order outside and within folders (but folders take priority in sorting).

- ATI Annotations: this is only for ATI (Annotations for Transparent Inquiry) projects for which the annotations are uploaded onto the data project as well, [see here for an example](#).
- Documentation: those always include the Readme, but can also include other documentation - e.g. interview questionnaires, data narratives, and most files that QDR generates in the curation process
- Code: code files include codebooks, replication files (e.g. .do and .qdp files) and any other scripts that are applied to the data
- Data: this tag is applied to all the research data in the project (usually most of the files)

To allocate tags:

1. Select all relevant files
2. Go to Edit Files > Tags > Select
3. Select (or unselect) all applicable tags
4. Save changes

Note that one file may have more than one tag. Also keep in mind that tagging files will sort them, so if you tag the data files first, you will find the Readme and other documentation at the bottom.

3.3.2. File Descriptions

In some cases, we might want to add a description to each file because of significant value added for secondary use or in case of copyright restrictions for individual files requiring a special note. The [United States Cold War Documents](#) project in the Trachtenberg Papers collection is one example of that.

The easiest way to edit multiple file descriptions at once is to select all relevant files and then going to Edit Files > Metadata. Write and record file descriptions beforehand in an excel file, most commonly the log or master list, and copy/paste the descriptions from there. For larger projects -- like the one above with 1,532 files -- Sebastian developed a functionality within DVCurator ([section 2.1.2.](#)) to batch upload file descriptions from a csv file.

Note: sometimes the depositor adds file descriptions when uploading the data. When you delete those files in order to upload the curated versions, those descriptions will have been removed as well. You can retrieve the file descriptions from the csv file generated by DVCurator. You will find it in the QDR project folder (same folder location as “Original Deposit” and “QDR Prepared”), entitled <DepositorName>_files_<date>.csv.

3.4. Project-Level Metadata

Project-level metadata is all the metadata that can be edited under the metadata tab on the data project page on Dataverse. Below is a list of the most important fields and applicable QDR standards:

1. **Title:** capitalize nouns, pronouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, and subordinate conjunctions. Lowercase articles (a, an, the), coordinating conjunctions, and prepositions. For supplemental data projects, begin title with “Data for:”
2. **Alternative URL:** insert link if project (with same data) exists somewhere else, e.g. [Steeves](#)
3. **QDRID:** automatically filled
4. **Creator:**
 - a. **Name:** <LastName>, <FirstName> - change to depositor name if QDR created the project
 - b. **Affiliation:** needs to be changed from “QDR IDP” to depositor’s affiliation
 - c. **ORCID:** We strongly encourage all depositors to create an ORCID (<https://orcid.org>) which serves as a unique identifier and links different works by academic authors. ORCID is a non-profit organization and this is completely free
5. **Contact:** same as above, add email address
6. **Description:** Ideally this would include a summary of the project and a data abstract.
 - a. **Project Summary:** this is often the abstract from the associated publication
 - b. **Data Abstract:** preferably answers four questions: (1) what are the data (e.g., interviews)? (2) how were the data selected (e.g., how interviewees were selected)? (3) what was the data collection strategy (both technically and substantially)? (4) how are the data organized (i.e., guiding structure, folders, documentation)?

- c. **Headlines:** if possible, keep within the following headlines for the sake of consistency: “Project Overview”, “Project Summary”, “Data Overview”, “”, “Data Analysis”, “Data Organization”.
 - d. **Text in description requires basic HTML::**
 - use <h3> tags for headlines within data deposits (e.g. overview field);
 - <p> tags to set paragraphs;
 - <i> for italics;
 - and to create ordered lists;
 - link text for hyperlinks;
 - (use </h3>, </p>, </i>, , at the end of respective sections)
7. **Subject:** should already be filled by depositor, but for most QDR projects select “Social Sciences” or “Medicine, Health and Life Sciences”
8. **Keywords:** Find at least three and up to 10 matching keywords (check the related publication if the depositor did not provide keywords). Use lower case as standard for all keywords. Geographical keywords (e.g. Latin America, Peru) are entered in “Geographic Coverage”, not in the keyword section.

We use two vocabularies: the ICPSR Thesaurus and, if needed, the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH). If the depositor has provided keywords that you cannot find good equivalents for in either of the vocabularies below, leave term as is.

- a. **ICPSR Thesaurus:** This is where we look first. The ICPSR Thesaurus is available [here](#). [A copy of the XML is available here](#). Enter “ICPSR Subject Thesaurus” for vocabulary and “<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/ICPSR/thesaurus/index>” for vocabulary URL.
- b. **LC Subject Headings (LCSH):** If we do not find matching keywords in the ICPSR Thesaurus, we search [here](#). Enter “LC Subject Headings (LCSH)” for vocabulary and “<http://id.loc.gov/authorities/subjects.html>” for vocabulary URL.
- c. **Example:** from the [Clarke Project](#):

The screenshot shows a form with three main input areas. On the left, there is a 'Keywords' field with a 'Contact' link above it. In the center, there is a 'Term' field containing the text 'refugees'. Below the 'Term' field is a 'Vocabulary URL' field containing the text 'https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/IC'. On the right, there is a 'Vocabulary' field containing the text 'ICPSR Subject Thesaurus'. To the right of the 'Vocabulary' field are two buttons: a plus sign (+) and a minus sign (-).

Note: in some instances, we may add keywords to group a set of data projects - for example, all data projects related to Covid-19 research will list “covid-19” as a keyword.

- 9. **Time Period Covered:** This is the time period covered by the data itself, e.g. 1815-1871 for archival documents of that period.
- 10. **Date of Data Collection:** This is the time period during which the researcher(s) collected the data, e.g. the time spent looking for documents in an archive.
- 11. **Type of Data Project:** We always add “qualitative data project” here first. Second, we add whether the project is a “thematic data project”, “supplemental data project”, “ATI data

supplement”, “active citation compilation”, or “pedagogical data project”. These are not all mutually exclusive, so a data project can be of multiple types (i.e., an ATI project will almost always also be a supplemental data project). [For a full description of project types click here.](#)

Note: sometimes the depositor will add specific metadata, such as the type of data deposited. We tend to retain these, but separate multiple entries into different fields. See [Steeves](#) for an example.

12. **Geographic Coverage:** Add geographical coverage (at least region), even if the depository does not do so explicitly.
13. **Related Publication:** Citation style is [Chicago Author-Date](#). Make sure to supply an appropriate identifier (isbn, doi). Insert the full URL under URL, but only the identifier portion in the identifier field, i.e.:

The screenshot shows a form with three input fields. The first field is labeled "Identifier Type" with a question mark icon and contains the text "doi". The second field is labeled "Identifier" with a question mark icon and contains the text "10.1371/journal.pone.0220460". The third field is labeled "URL" with a question mark icon and contains the text "https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0220460".

14. **Language:** Select appropriate language(s).
15. **Grant Information:** We always ask if the project was funded and record the funding entity here.
16. **Related Data Projects:** insert full citation and DOI if project with related data exists somewhere else (such as quantitative data stored on OSF, ICPSR). Also fill out if depositor has other related projects on QDR.

The above are the most commonly used metadata fields, but the list is not exclusive. If appropriate, other fields should be filled - e.g., contributors.

3.5. Terms of Use, Access Conditions, Restrictions and Permissions

Next, we edit the terms of use, access conditions, check file restrictions and assign permissions for registered users. Once you are familiar with the general instructions, you can skip directly to the standard and special deposit sections depending on the data project you are working on.

3.5.1. General Instructions

The terms of use and access conditions outline the conditions and licenses under which documentation and data files deposited in the project can be accessed and used. The terms of use are always identical to the terms of access. Follow the steps below:

- Go to the “Terms” tab in the data project and select “Edit Terms Requirements”.
- *Always* select “No, do not apply CC0” under “Waiver” (we never apply the CC0 - Public Domain Dedication).
- Insert in the “Terms of Use” box (which will appear underneath) the appropriate terms language in html format, based on the templates for standard and special deposit types further below in this section.
- If you added the terms of access language during file upload (cf. [section 3.2.6](#)), those will appear in the “Terms of Access” field. Otherwise, copy/paste the Terms of Use language here.
- Check or Uncheck the “Enable Access Request” button under “Request Access”. It will be already checked if selected during file upload (cf. [section 3.2.7](#)), but you can edit it here. Instructions on when to enable or disable access requests are found in the standard and special deposit type sections further below.

File restrictions and permissions are the technological implementation of the access conditions, meaning that they determine what files in a data project users can view or download on the Dataverse platform. Follow the steps below:

- Check that all files that should be restricted (i.e. all data files) are indeed restricted (this is usually done at upload). You can restrict/unrestrict files either individually using the file options button >Restrict/Unrestrict or several at once, by selecting multiple files and clicking Edit Files>Restrict/Unrestrict.
- For standard projects, go to Edit Data Project → Permissions → File, select all data files and authorize access by :authenticated_users (will come up when you type :au into the search). This will allow all QDR users to view and download the restricted data after logging in. Consult the standard and special deposit type sections below for instructions on when not to assign those permissions.

3.5.2. Standard Data Projects

Terms of Use/Access

This is the template for standard projects in which all registered users have access to the data:

<p>Documentation freely accessible under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 license.</p>

<p>Data files accessible without restrictions for all registered QDR users under our Standard Download Agreement.</p>

Access Request

Enable

Permissions

Authorize access for :authenticated_users to all restricted files

3.5.3. Projects with Data under Copyright

Terms of Use/Access

This is the template for projects with data under copyright and not otherwise restricted:

<p>Documentation freely accessible under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 license.</p>

<p>Data files accessible without restrictions for all registered QDR users under our Standard Download Agreement.</p>

<p>Files currently under copyright are restricted and not accessible to users. Where available, the year they enter the public domain (and will be available through QDR) is indicated in the file description.</p>

Access Request

Enable

Permissions

Authorize selective access for :authenticated_users to all restricted files that do not constitute copyrighted data

Special Instructions:

- Create a reminder for the curation team to lift restrictions (i.e. grant permission to :authenticated_users) for copyrighted data the year those data enter the public domain.

- Edit file descriptions as described in [section 2.3.2](#), and see [section 3.2.2](#) on how to edit file descriptions for large projects.

3.5.4. Projects with Sensitive Data

Terms of Use/Access

Below is an example of language employed for deposits with special access restrictions due to sensitive data (note that those are custom-tailored to each special deposit):

```
<p>Documentation freely accessible under the <a
href="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/">Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0
license</a>.</p>
```

```
<p>Data access requires submission of a research plan and proof of completed CITI Human Subjects
Research (HSR) training or equivalent.</p>
```

Access Request

Enable

Permissions

Do not grant any permissions (except in mixed data projects, in which case grant selective access as appropriate)

Special Instructions:

- See [section 5.2](#), for how to handle access requests to restricted files.

3.5.5. Projects with Data under Embargo

Terms of Use/Access

Use the following language with a specific date as arranged with depositor:

```
<p>Documentation freely accessible under the <a
href="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/">Creative Commons Attribution-Share
Alike 4.0 license</a>.</p>
```

```
<p>Data files are under embargo until <month> <day>, <year>, and will be accessible thereafter
without restrictions for all registered QDR users under our <a
href="https://qdr.syr.edu/discover/standarddownload">Standard Download Agreement</a>.</p>
```

Note: "Standard Download Agreement" should be replaced with a special download agreement when appropriate.

Access Request

Disable

Permissions

Do not grant any permissions

Special Instructions:

- Create an alert (or have a Zoho user do so) in Zoho CRM to remind the depositor 2-4 weeks prior to the end of embargo to inform them that the new terms will be coming into force; the depositor will not have to submit a new Deposit Agreement.
- Create a reminder for the curation team to change the wording on Terms of Use and Terms and Terms of Access to new conditions and to alter file permissions accordingly and enabling access requests for any restricted files on the agreed-upon date.

Note: IQSS was planning on developing an Embargo feature for Dataverse in Q3 2020 - now delayed to 2021 (<https://github.com/IQSS/Dataverse/issues/4052>). When implemented, it might provide an automated timed-released process and affect the procedure outlined above.

3.6. Thumbnails

We select thumbnails for each data project, to replace the standard document image with an image taken from the data project. This will also be the image used if the data project is featured on the homepage.

To edit thumbnails, go to Edit Data Project > Thumbnails + Widgets > Thumbnails and upload an image from a suitable file in the data project. (An easy way to do this from files other than the available ones is by using Windows' snipping tool. Do take care to not select an image from a file with sensitive information.)

Note that, as of now, the file extension (.png, .jpg) needs to be in lowercase. File extensions in upper case will fail due to a current issue in Dataverse (see [GitHub issue on IQSS](#)).

3.7. Set Google Scholar Alert

When we receive a data project that is a supplement for a journal, we often don't hear about the article getting published (even though we ask them to). Therefore, we want to set up a Google Scholar Alert for the title of the data set.

To do so, follow the steps below:

1. Go to [Google Scholar](https://scholar.google.com) and search for the depositor's name
2. Locate and click on the "Create alert" button on the left
3. Edit the alert query to reflect (at minimum): author:<FirstName> author:<LastName>
4. Set the email as: qualitativedatarepository@gmail.com
5. Click "CREATE ALERT"

The screenshot shows the Google Scholar Alerts interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Google Scholar logo. Below it, the 'Alerts' section is visible. The 'Alert query' field contains 'author:stefania author:borghini'. The 'Email' field contains 'qualitativedatarepository@gmail.com'. The 'Number of results' dropdown is set to 'Show up to 10 results'. At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: 'Update results' and 'CREATE ALERT'.

In the future, we will likely want to switch to identification via ORCID - that is, once the identifier obtains sufficient coverage.

3.8. Set Private URL

If needed, QDR staff can create and share a private URL that allows a non-logged in user to review a project before it is published. This should be done only with permission / request by a depositor. The expected use case is if a journal editor or reviewer needs to access the data prior to final publication of a deposit.

To do, go to Edit Data Project > Private URL. This URL becomes invalid when a project is published.

4. Publication Procedure

This section addresses the steps after all operations on Dataverse are finalized and how to publish the project.

4.1. Depositor Review and Agreement

Make sure everything is in order and allow the depositor to review one more time. If the depositor requests any changes, implement them as necessary. Once the depositor is satisfied, request that they submit a Standard or Special Deposit Agreement. The Standard Deposit Agreement is available [here](#). The Special Deposit Agreement is available [here](#).

4.2. Publishing

Conduct a final review of the entire data project -- especially worth reviewing are the access permissions applied (that they correspond to any explicit instructions) and the README file. Once published, editing a data project will force a version update and we want to avoid that as much as possible (silent updates are possible if the data remains the same, but we want to avoid that). At least two sets of eyes should have checked the project before publication.

If everything is in order, add today's date as the distribution date -- click "Publish", and confirm!

Once the project is published, we tweet about the data project on Twitter from the [QDR account](#) and tag @depositor (ask for depositor's Twitter account in correspondence).

Note:

- *Remember to close the project and all related issues in GitHub after publication*
- *Ask a Super User to verify that archiving is successful after publication - under "Versions", the column "Archived" should read "Complete" (this is not visible to curators and admins).*

5. After Publication

5.1. Editing Post-Publication

We try to avoid it as much as possible, but in some cases minor or major edits need to be done to the data project. All file changes will force a major version update (e.g. 1.0→ 2.0). All metadata changes let you choose between a minor (1.0 → 1.1) or major version update. We will typically do minor.

Whenever you do a major update, describe the changes between versions in the “Notes” field, with the following title, e.g.: <h3>Update Notes for Version 2</h3>

If you make changes to a published data project, that project will exist twice in the Dataverse catalog (for administrators/curators): once as the published project, once as a draft. In order for your changes to take effect on the published project, you need to publish it again.

Note: here as well, after any edits ask a Super User to verify that archiving is successful - under “Versions”, the column “Archived” should read “Complete” (this is not visible to curators and admins).

5.2. Access Requests

When users request access to restricted files, these requests are sent to qdr@syr.edu.

Follow the steps below:

1. Add the user requesting access to Zoho as a “Contact,” assign the “Controlled Data User” tag to the contact and -- if access does get granted -- set a reminder for checking in on data use/disposition;
2. Check to see what requirements for access are;
3. Inform the user of any requirements to access the data (e.g., submission of a research plan), the procedure for granting data access (i.e., whether QDR is authorized to grant access or if the depositor needs to be involved), and have them complete the special download agreement: <https://qdr.syr.edu/discover/specialdownload> ;
4. Review the information provided and make a decision (or defer to depositor) on whether or not to grant access to the data;

- If access is to be granted, go to Edit > Permissions > File - you should see options to grant or reject requests for each user that requested access as shown below:

Email	Files	Access	
ngen@syr.edu	1 File	✓ Grant	⊘ Reject
069@smail.iitn	45 Files	✓ Grant	⊘ Reject
@hotmail.com	1 File	✓ Grant	⊘ Reject
by33@email.pl	1 File	✓ Grant	⊘ Reject

- Click on the hyperlinked text showing the number of files requested (e.g., “45 Files”) and confirm that those files correspond to the data that access can be granted to.
- Edit if necessary (uncheck boxes next to files for which access cannot be granted) and click “Grant”.
- If you want to grant access to files a user did not click “request access” for (those will not appear in the list of files requested above), go to “Grant Access to Users/Groups”, select all applicable files, enter the user’s username, and click “Grant”.

All users who were granted access to restricted data will be listed on the same page, below the list of users with open requests, e.g.:

1 Users/Groups			
User/Group Name (Affiliation)	ID	Files	Access
Anyone with a QDR account	:authenticated-users	27 Files	✕ Remove Access

Use this page to track who has access to restricted data in a data project and edit access privileges if necessary.

5.3. Lifting Copyright Restrictions

For data projects with data files restricted due to copyright reasons, these restrictions need to be lifted the year the data enter the public domain. For example, for the [Hispaniola data from Don Leonard](#), we will have to lift restrictions on files almost every year for the next four decades.

5.4. Removing Embargo

For data projects with data files restricted due to a timed embargo, restrictions need to be lifted on the agreed-upon date. There should be reminders in Zoho and in the Curation Team roadmap set at the time of initial publication (see [Borghini 2021](#) for QDR's first example). Give advance notice to depositor, change terms of use/access, enable access request and assign file permissions as necessary.